

Green chemistry approaches and innovative drug delivery systems towards reducing environmental impact in antiparasitic drug discovery

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The valorization of macroalgae from the portuguese coast for the green synthesis of graphene quantum dots for pH-sensitive theranostic

Marlene Lúcio^{a,b,c}

^a Centro de Física das Universidades do Minho e Porto (CF-UM-UP); ^b Centro de Biologia Molecular e Ambiental da Universidade do Minho (CBMA), ^c Laboratório de Física para Materiais e Tecnologias Emergentes (*LaPMET*)

mlucio@fisica.uminho.pt

The green synthesis of nanomaterials has been intensively investigated because of the increase in world population, scarcity of primary and energy resources and environmental pollution with potential harm to human health.

Graphene-based nanomaterials (GBNs), namely graphene quantum dots (GQDs) can be obtained from underexploited natural resources or even from biomass residues by energy-efficient one-pot synthesis routes. Moreover, due to their stable and tunable photoluminescence, biocompatibility, and easy surface functionalization, GQDs show promise as theranostic systems, as they simultaneously present bioimaging and drug delivery valences [1,2].

This work aimed to produce GQDs responsive to pH variations, by a one-pot green microwave assisted synthesis from an opportunistic Portuguese macroalgae coast, *Saccorhiza polyschides*. GQDs demonstrated an effective fluorescence resonance energy transfer (FRET) for the sensitive bioimaging. The GQDs exhibited fluorescence emission at ≈ 420 nm, while in the presence of drug due to FRET process between GQDs and drug, the fluorescence of GQDs was efficiently quenched, meanwhile, a strong fluorescence emission at 550 nm for drug is provided. The effective conjugation between GQDs (donor) and drug (acceptor) through π - π stacking and hydrophobic interactions increases the emission signal of drug. After the release of drug, favored at acidic pH, FRET efficiency is significantly affected given the increase in the distance of the donor-acceptor pair.

We propose to conjugate graphene oxide quantum dots (GQD) with drug (GQD@drug) to be loaded in nonlamellar lipid carriers to improve biodistribution and in addition to produce a multifunctional nanocarrier as a promising drug delivery vehicle for the diagnosis and image-guided therapy. So far, we have developed these nanosystems for cancer therapy, but they are easily adapted as delivery systems for other drugs.

References

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